

**PROBLEMS OF CHOOSING A TERMINOLOGICAL LEXICAL
MINIMUM IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING****Shakhlo Urunova**

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To develop a linguodidactic system of teaching a specialist language, it is important that students strictly choose the language material, which allows you to maximize the activation of the process of mastering the English language in connection with the chosen specialty. It is necessary to select frequent lexical units, typical syntactic constructions, to arrange them in a certain way, which can be the basis for the easy assimilation of students and their subsequent use in active communication. All this requires adherence to the principle of consistency in the description of language and speech materials, which allows you to develop the ability to self-learn based on a conscious and practical method, actively transfer the acquired knowledge and formed skills to unfamiliar language and speech materials in a new context of real communication. Thanks to this, teaching terminological vocabulary to students of a non-philological orientation in teaching their specialty in a foreign language will serve to develop their professional lexical knowledge. All this indicates the scientific justification of the need to choose a lexical minimum.

Currently, the question of the choice of lexical material, taking into account the language of specialization, is the main issue in linguodidactics. Academician N.M.Shansky, G.G.Gorodilova, S.G.Barkhudarov, L.G.Sayahova, N.Z.Bakeeva, V.I.Zimin, L.N.In the work of Novikov and others, issues of lexical minimum selection were considered. These scientists noted that the further development of educational lexicography, the development of the theory and practice of compiling various educational dictionaries, first of all, the development of complex and aspect dictionaries of an active type, which, first of all, will be oriented to the communicative.

The concept of terminological minimum is related to the term "lexical minimum" in the methodology. While most Methodist scholars argue that these two concepts are indistinguishable from each other, O.L.Yarichenko mentions that there is a partial difference between these two concepts [7;104]. While the two terms are related, there must be a clear boundary in their methodological structure, the scope of their adoption, their functions, and the methods of their presentation. That is, when common words are compared with special words – terms according to the characteristics of the sources of each language unit, it is

noticeable that they are used by potential special professions and are distinguished by special features.

When we analyze the reasons for the origin of these two concepts, we witness that none of them has been studied as a separate scientific concept and that only their common characteristics have been studied. The term lexical minimum originated from the framework of a particular educational program requirement, with the concept of terminological minimum arising from the reason that LSP (Language for Special Purposes (terminology)), i.e., is lacking the necessary training material for a special purpose language.

The term "lexical minimum" is common in educational contexts, and is the choice of a dictionary source in a level appropriate to the level of learners [6; 47]. In particular, such a lexicon is considered important and necessary. The lexicograph Dictionary defines: "lexical minimum-words selected according to the degree of multiple application and proximity of meanings are considered essential in conducting dialogue in the language and for the purposes of language acquisition. Such lexical choice focuses primarily on words that are statistically multiple-use as well as stylistically neutral and with strong semantic meaning, and words like this help the learner to communicate in everyday communicative situations [2; 45-b].

The "terminological minimum" is a practical tool in the selection of special lexicon focused on teaching to different levels of learners in special purpose language learning (LSP) courses [5; 134].

S.Grusza defines a "terminological minimum " as a vocabulary wealth belonging to a specific area of specialization of a specific language, selected on the basis of certain criteria. In addition to his opinion, the scientist notes that: the "terminological minimum" is, together with this, a set of dictionaries that allow representatives of a particular group to conduct communication based on their communicative needs" [1; 44-b].

X.Kasmarek notes: "in the dominant role in the teaching process, not only the teacher, but also textbooks, teaching aids and of course the lexical minimum, which are in accordance with the curriculum, according to which the glottodidactic research materials are calculated, are of fundamental importance in optimizing the course of the lesson. A special-purpose lexical minimum is considered informative educational material, divided into direct (manual for independent learning) and indirect (as a resource for textbooks, teaching materials) types, both of which serve to increase the communicative and professional competence of students [4;27-28-b].

From the above, we can conclude that the “lexical minimum” is a component of linguistic competence and is considered to contain a vocabulary wealth that is mentally mastered by a person, which helps students to communicate in accordance with different levels of competence. From this we can conclude that a lexical minimum is formed in accordance with the student level (elementary, pre-intermediate, intermediate, etc).

The importance of choosing a terminological minimum in organizing the methodology for teaching terminological lexicon is based on the fact that, in addition to conducting conversations on special topics, it is necessary to create a solid terminological base that provides understanding of the maximum number of terms when reading original scientific and technical literature in its specialty, as well as the The choice of the terminological minimum was based on the fact that the criteria that guarantee the effective formation of the terminological reserve that will cover the maximum, the structured terminological minimum methodological classification, distribution and statistical presentation should go through stages, from the dynamic stage to serve the formation of student skills.

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